

INSURANCE INDUSTRY IN THE CURRENT REALITIES OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: The article examines the importance of the life insurance industry, shows its historical formation in Uzbekistan and the main stages of development. A consistent analysis of changes in legislative norms and regulation of the life insurance industry reveals the methodological aspect of market research. With a low level of a number of indicators of the functioning of the life insurance market in Uzbekistan, there has been a significant growth of the market in recent years, and its further development is due, on the one hand, to the ability of insurers to introduce new insurance services and implement a competent investment policy, and on the other – the interest of domestic insurers in the availability and expansion of insurance coverage, the determining factors of which are the aging of the population and the increase in life expectancy. Based on the analysis of the current state and development problems, proposals for the further development of the life insurance industry are given.

Key words: life insurance, insurance market of Uzbekistan, insurance premium, insurance payments, legislative regulation of insurance, history of life insurance in Uzbekistan, problems of insurance development.

Insurance companies in Uzbekistan increased the volume of premiums collected in 2021 by 68.6% compared to 2020. The figure exceeded 3.7 trillion soums.

The volume of premiums collected in Uzbekistan relative to the country's GDP is relatively small and is equal to about 0.5% at the end of the year. However, this indicator is planned to increase in 2022 to 0.8%.

Worldwide, the insurance business is growing by an average of 3% per year. Over 10 years, insurance premiums have increased from 2.6 trillion euros in 2008 to 3.6 trillion in 2018.

Insurance premiums per capita are also growing, on average they amount to 847 euros per person. At the same time, the dynamics of growth by region is changing. The traditional leaders — North America and Western Europe - lost 4% and 6% of the total insurance fees, respectively. While China, for example, has almost tripled in relation to other players in 10 years — from 4% to 11%.

Premiums in the life insurance segment more than doubled (from 334.4 to 717 billion) at the end of the year. Chairman of the Board of Directors of the Association of Professional Participants of the Insurance Market of Uzbekistan Oybek Khalilov notes that such a sharp increase is due to the recovery of the market after the pandemic of 2020. If compared with 2019, the growth was 22.3%. In the total premium portfolio, this area occupies about 19%, and in terms of insurance payments, the sector is the leader – 616.3 billion. This is slightly more than half of the total amount of reimbursements paid in Uzbekistan. The development of the direction is mainly due to voluntary insurance.

Insurance premiums per capita in the world are equal to 847 euros, in Uzbekistan — 5 euros. This indicates the low price of the product. At the same time, the leader of the list — Hong Kong — has this figure of 7.5 thousand euros. Nigeria has a similar indicator with Uzbekistan (5 euros).

Another trend in the global market, which the conference participants recommended to take a closer look at in Uzbekistan, is the introduction of a risk-based approach. Insurance companies assess not just the risks associated with the premium, the obligations of the insurance company, but at the same time assess the

risks of assets, credit, market. This allows you to more actively manage the capital of the insurance company.

This trend is also spreading to emerging markets, which is due to the desire to attract foreign investors, for whom a risk-based approach from the point of view of capital management is more understandable and gives more opportunities in terms of comparability.

Voluntary general insurance (DOS) is in the second position in terms of the growth rate of premiums. The volume increase was 64.7%. The segment took 68% of the market (premium portfolio - 2.5 trillion). It accounts for more than a third of payments (433.7 billion). The aviation industry in this segment ranks first in terms of growth in relative terms. Insurance, which involves the payment of compensation for the loss or damage of an aircraft or its equipment, collected premiums of 9.66 billion. The growth was 470.4%. As part of the responsibility of air carriers to individuals and legal entities, there were 1.5 billion (+487.8%) in premiums.

The main focus of DOS is credit insurance. Its share is 23.7% of all premiums in this segment. Over the past year, more than 600 billion soums were collected, which is 83.4% higher than it was a year earlier. In second place in terms of premiums is land vehicle insurance (307.4 billion), and in third place is general civil liability (207 billion).

General compulsory insurance (OOS) took 13% of the market. The volume of premiums collected amounted to 476.7 billion. Almost half of this amount is taken up by civil liability insurance of vehicle owners - 229.12 billion (+30.6%). This is followed by the civil liability of the employer -165.6 billion. This is 62.3% more than a year earlier. The top three are closed by construction and installation risks - 42.11 billion (+63.6%).

According to those responsible, the government of Uzbekistan expects that the contribution of the insurance sector to GDP will grow to 0.8% in 2022. It is planned to achieve the goal through the development of new directions.

In October 2021, the President of the Republic signed a decree "On additional measures to digitalize the insurance market and develop the life insurance sector."

"The tax benefits announced in this document in the life insurance segment both in terms of the insurance company's profit tax and in terms of income tax allow us to accelerate the development of long-term life insurance and will contribute to the expansion of the list of services".

According to the decree, government securities linked to inflation will appear in Uzbekistan from July 1, 2022. One of the points of the document is stated as follows: "The Ministry of Finance should develop proposals and recommendations on the direction of government securities linked to inflation in order for insurance organizations to invest funds generated by insurance premiums from voluntary pension insurance and types of long-term (five years or more) life insurance".

In an interview with Kursiv, the director of the Kapital Depozit investment company, Farrukh Khodjaev, noted that life insurance is, as a rule, a long-term process.

"In addition to the main goal — to provide a safety cushion for loved ones in case something happens to you, life insurance has other opportunities that allow you to accumulate capital for long-term purposes, for example, educating children at university, saving for an increase in pension. In conditions of high inflation, which is very important for Uzbekistan, the attractiveness and value of long-term life insurance is greatly reduced"

In such conditions, it is more profitable for people to keep money in hard currency and save savings through other instruments, for example, bank deposits. This resolution provides for protection against inflation of citizens' funds aimed at long-term life insurance.

The republic has recently been undergoing enormous reforms in all sectors of the economy. Insurance is an indispensable tool for business development. In addition, insurance services for the population are also considered one of the important factors of this sector. The main task of the state policy in the field of

insurance is the formation and improvement of the legislative framework of insurance activity, forms and methods of supervision over it. The Government's policy of regulating insurance activity creates all the necessary conditions for the dynamic development of the insurance market, ensures a high level of creative processes in its development. These measures are key factors in the formation of a modern, full-fledged and competitive insurance market. The purpose of the state policy in the field of insurance is to form an insurance system capable of effectively protecting the property interests of citizens, legal entities and the state in the event of insured events. The adoption of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4412 dated August 2, 2019 "On measures to reform and ensure the accelerated development of the insurance market of the Republic of Uzbekistan" plays an important role in the development of the insurance market.

In recent years, the activities of insurance organizations have been experiencing a faster growth rate in the types of voluntary insurance, which indicates the real development of insurance and an increase in the level of confidence in the services of insurance companies. So, as of January 1, 2022, the number of insurance organizations was 42, of which 8 organizations are engaged in life insurance. As a result of the measures taken to increase the authorized capital, during 2021 the total volume of the authorized capital of insurance organizations increased by 7.4% and amounted to 1,545.78 billion.soums. By the end of 2021, the investment portfolio of insurers increased by 10.8% and amounted to 3.74 trillion. soums. Most of the investments were accounted for by bank deposits, which increased by 21.4% during the period under review and amounted to 2.21 trillion.soums. Investments in securities by the end of 2021 increased by 14.3% and amounted to 1095.97 billion.soums or 29.3% of all investments of insurance organizations.

During 2021, general insurance premiums collected by insurers increased by 68.6% and amounted to 3.73 trillion.soums. At the same time, in the period under review, life insurance premiums increased by 114.4% and amounted to 717.03

billion. soums. In particular, premiums from voluntary types of insurance increased by 74.35% and amounted to 3.23 trillion.soums or 86.54% (in 2020: 83.69%) of all collected premiums of insurance organizations. At the same time, during the period under review, premiums from mandatory types of insurance services increased by 39.17% and amounted to 502.35 billion rubles.soums.

According to the results of 2021, there was a corresponding increase in insurance payments to insurance premiums. Thus, during the period under review, insurance payments increased by 67.1% and amounted to 1,232.3 billion.soums. Of these, 84.51% is accounted for by insurance payments for voluntary types of insurance, amounting to 1,041.4 billion. soums.

Despite a fairly wide branch network of insurance organizations, the main business is still concentrated in the metropolitan region. At the same time, 78.4% of the collected premiums by the end of 2021 fall to the share of the city of Tashkent and the Tashkent region.

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